

OPTIMIZING WORKPLACE SAFETY: THE VITAL ROLE OF OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH AND SAFETY COMMITTEES IN PREVENTING AND REDUCING WORK-RELATED ACCIDENTS AND ILLNESSES IN KOTA BUKIT INDAH INDUSTRIAL ESTATE PURWAKARTA, INDONESIA

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Abstract

Currently, the industrial sector in Indonesia is developing very rapidly in line with advances in science and technology. The use of technology in the industrial world also varies greatly from simple technology to complex technology. However, even though a culture of occupational safety and health has been promoted since half a century ago, work accidents in Indonesia are still relatively high. Recognizing that the involvement of workers in the workplace can be achieved, among others, through having representatives of the workforce in implementing occupational safety and health and establishing an Occupational Safety and Health organization. So, the Government issued Minister of Manpower Regulation number 4 of 1987 concerning Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee and Procedures for Appointing Work Safety Experts, Article 1 (d) explained that what is meant by the Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee, hereinafter referred to as Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee. The Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee is an auxiliary body in the workplace which is a forum for cooperation between employers and workers to develop cooperative mutual understanding and effective participation in the implementation of occupational safety and health. However, until now in the implementation of occupational safety and health, a competency system has not been developed that includes the roles and duties of each Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee team, including the Chair of Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee and members of Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee. Even though the competency system is needed so that the implementation of an occupational safety and health management system can be carried out quickly and effectively to minimize the impact of work accidents that may occur in the company.

Keywords: Competence, Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee.

INTRODUCTION

This article discusses the importance of the Role of the Occupational Safety and Health Committee in Preventing and Reducing Work Accidents and Occupational Diseases in the Industrial Area of Bukit Indah Purwakarta City. This issue is crucial to discuss because Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee is one of the organizations formed to ensure the sustainability and success of companies, including ensuring occupational safety and health (OSH). The policy of protecting workers has been widely implemented in various

countries. The implementation of occupational health and safety not only provides protection for workers but also for production resources, which in turn can enhance the efficiency and productivity of the company. In addition, the economic aspect is also influenced by occupational health and safety, where the implementation of standards can help reduce medical costs, improve efficiency, and decrease work accidents, thus affecting the overall performance of the company (Lin & Mills, 2001). Countries that effectively implement occupational safety and health guarantees tend to have more productive, prosperous, and secure workers in the workplace. This not only has an impact on improving company performance but also helps the government reduce costs arising from work accidents and lower the rate of work-related accidents and illnesses (Fernández-Muñiz et al., 2007).

The main focus in Indonesia is to enhance the safety and health of workers in many sectors such as industry, agriculture, mining, and manufacturing through the implementation of OSH measures. The implementation of international occupational health and safety standards, regulated by organizations such as the International Labour Organization (ILO), World Health Organization (WHO), and International Organization for Standardization (ISO), aims to safeguard the well-being of workers and enhance the efficiency and productivity of companies (Coglianese & Lazer, 2003). Therefore, the implementation of international occupational health and safety standards in Indonesia is not only crucial for protecting workers and production resources, but also has significant economic implications by improving working conditions, reducing costs, and enhancing overall productivity. Thus, occupational safety and health are crucial aspects in maintaining the well-being of workers and enhancing overall company performance (Nugraha, 2023)

Specifically, Indonesia has issued various regulations related to occupational safety, including Law No. 1 of 1970 concerning Occupational Safety and Health, which provides a basic framework for preventing work accidents and occupational diseases in the workplace. The key and core of the Occupational Safety and Health Law are related to the involvement of workers and management as well as the work organizations within it to improve OSH standards. In addition, Minister of Manpower Regulation No. 4 of 1987 regarding Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee and Procedures for Appointing Occupational Safety Experts explain that the Occupational Safety and Health Committee, hereinafter referred to as Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee, is an auxiliary body in the workplace that is a forum for cooperation between employers and workers to develop cooperation, mutual understanding, and effective participation in implementing occupational safety and health (Wang, 2021).

As stipulated in the Occupational Safety and Health Law, Article 10 (1), which states that "the Minister of Manpower is authorized to establish Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee to develop cooperation, mutual understanding, and effective participation of employers or management and workers in the workplace to carry out joint duties and obligations in the field of occupational safety and health to facilitate production efforts." Developing cooperation, mutual understanding, and effective participation mean a form of involvement from both parties. Meanwhile, the duties and obligations of both parties are to

facilitate production efforts through improving OSH performance. In this regard, Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee plays a central role in ensuring OSH performance in the workplace (Susanti, 2017; Olanipekun, 2021).

Improving OSH performance can be more easily achieved if the management side collaborates with workers (through the Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee forum), consults on potential hazards, discusses them, and finds solutions to all OSH issues that arise in the workplace. Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee as a forum for OSH discussions can bring together management and worker representatives to consider general OSH issues in the workplace comprehensively, plan, implement, and monitor OSH programs that have been established (Ayuni, 2022).

The Indonesian Government has enacted Law No. 1 of 1970 concerning occupational safety aimed at protecting workers in carrying out their work for the sake of their well-being and improving company production and productivity, as well as ensuring occupational safety in the workplace. The Occupational Safety and Health Law states that it has given responsibility to company management to implement Work Accident Prevention. Although many companies are not fully aware of workplace hazards related to occupational safety regulations, resulting in many violations and requiring supervision to prevent accidents and occupational diseases (Situngkir, 2021).

Workplace accidents are a public concern because they are very detrimental to workers and companies. Workers are harmed because they experience pain, disability, and even death, while companies also suffer due to workplace accidents, which involve damaged assets such as resources, machinery parts, materials, equipment, or work environments. Consequently, this can lead to disruptions in the production process. Based on Government Regulation No. 2 of 2017 concerning Industrial Infrastructure Development, one of the industrial areas designated as a National Vital Object of Indonesia is the Bukit Indah Purwakarta Industrial Area (Eom, 2022).

Despite being regulated accordingly, during the implementation of policies on Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee and Procedures for Appointing Occupational Safety Experts, cases of work accidents and occupational diseases still occur in companies in the industrial area of Bukit Indah Purwakarta. Incidents of work accidents and occupational related diseases in the industrial area of Bukit Indah Purwakarta are part of the Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee role that is not yet sufficiently effective (Alfian, R., 2024). This proves that the top management through Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee is not competent enough in understanding occupational safety and health in the company's work area (Ndana, 2018). This article discusses "The Role of Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee in preventing and reducing work accidents and occupational diseases in the industrial area of Bukit Indah Purwakarta".

OSH Policy for Achieving Worker Welfare

1. Public Policy

Public policy focuses on what Dewey (1927) referred to as "the public and its problems". Public policy addresses how these issues and problems are structured and defined, and how they are placed on the policy and political agendas. Furthermore, public policy is a study of "how, why, and what the effects of government action and inaction are" (Heidenheimer et al., 1990: 3). Or, as stated by Dye, public policy is the study of "what governments do, why governments take action, and what the consequences of these actions are" (Dye, 1976: 1).

For a long time, scholars have endeavored to find a definition that satisfies all parties regarding Public Policy as a distinct field of study. However, even essential books like the Handbook of Public Policy and the Handbook of Public Policy Analysis do not begin their writings with an adequate definition. With a very general definition, policy can be interpreted as "whatever government choose to do or not to do" (Dye, 1987,1) or "the relationship of governmental unit of its environment" (Eyestone 1971:18) or "the actions, objectives, and pronouncements of governments on particular matters, the step they take (or fail to take) to implement them, and the explanations they give for what happens (or does not happen)". Which can be understood as all government actions, objectives, and statements on a particular field, the steps they take (or do not take) to implement them, and the explanations they provide for what happens (and does not happen) (Wilson, 2006:154).

The above definitions are actually quite accurate in the sense that they can encompass almost everything considered as public policy. However, they are too general and have very limited capacity to encapsulate every thought that can distinguish Public Policy studies from Political Science, Welfare Economics, and even Public Administration. These definitions do not contain clear boundaries that isolate the intellectual search of Public Policy scholars and distinguish them from Political Science scholars who examine infrastructure and superstructure institutions and even voter behavior. After all, what the government as an incumbent chooses to do or not to do will ultimately relate to the ballot box at the time of elections?

Anderson (1994:5) provides a narrower definition; he states public policy as "a purposes course of action or inaction undertaken by an actor or set of actors in dealing with a problem or matter of concern". Public policy is the action taken with intent by an actor or a set of actors in addressing a problem or matter of concern. This means that public policy is not random but has a purpose and intent; public policy is carried out by public authorities; public policy consists of a pattern of actions within a specific timeframe; public policy is the result of demand, it is a series of government actions directed in response to pressure on an issue. Public policy can be positive (actions taken) or negative (actions not taken). Regarding this definition, public policy can be regarded as a tool or instrument of government. Public policy is a series of actions and decisions taken by public authorities regarding a particular issue.

In Indonesia, public policy established is influenced by the socio-economic conditions of its society, whether related to the level of education, the income level of the society, the poverty rate, the quality of life, or the level of competitiveness.

The institutional and political system in Indonesia influences and is also influenced by the socio-economic conditions of Indonesian society. These institutions are very complex, covering legal systems, economic systems, political systems, and cultural systems (Wibowo, 2015).

In this institution, political parties, the government (central and regional), bureaucracy, parliament, and organizations play a role. They determine what policies the government will take. Policy outputs can take the form of Laws, Government Regulations, Presidential Regulations, or Regional Regulations, whether related to education, health, financial, or other areas that touch the lives of the public.

Political parties and bureaucracy are considered the most prominent in determining public policy. Golkar Party during the New Order era, the PDI-P party during Megawati's government, and the Democratic Party during SBY's government are examples of political parties that dominantly determine the pattern of policies taken by the government (Fefta, 2023).

2. Policy Analysis According to Dunn

Public policy addresses how public issues and concerns are constructed and defined, and how they are placed on policy agendas and political agendas (Parsons, 2001). Therefore, analysis is necessary to understand the substance of policy, which includes information about the issues to be addressed and the possible impacts of the implemented policy (Dunn, 2004).

Policy analysis involves the application of various research methods conducted by a policy analyst or group of analysts aimed at obtaining various data and processing it into relevant information regarding a policy (policy information) to be used in assisting in the formulation of complex and structured public issues (well-structured policy problem), thus facilitating the formulation and selection of various policy alternatives to be used to solve a policy issue and recommended to policy makers (Abd. Rahman, 2023).

A policy analyst works through the stages of the policy formulation process, whether technocratic or political. In the technocratic process, policy analysts use methodological skills and policy substance to process data into policy information, making it easier for them to formulate several policy alternative options (Safaei, 2023).

These policy alternatives are then proposed to policymakers as policy recommendations. In the political process, policy analysts use policy information to garner support from stakeholders so that the stages of problem formulation, alternative identification, and policy recommendation can proceed smoothly. In this process, an analyst needs to have political skills to build relationships with policy actors in both government and non-governmental institutions, including civil society groups.

This is important to ensure that the policy information generated by analysts can be understood by stakeholders and used as a basis for decision-making (Kowalska-Pyzalska, 2024).

Borrowing the terms used by Parsons (2001), it can be concluded that an analyst will work in two broad categories:

- 1) Policy process analysis, which involves defining problems, setting agendas, formulating policies, making decisions, and implementing and evaluating policies (Ávila-Gutiérrez, 2022).
- 2) Analysis within and for policy processes, which includes the use of technical analysis, research, and advocacy in defining problems, decision-making, implementation, and evaluation (Patton, 2023).

Public policy analysis aims to provide recommendations to assist policymakers in solving public problems. In public policy analysis, there is information related to public issues and arguments about various policy alternatives, as considerations or inputs to policymakers (Kitchener, 2023).

Public policy analysis based on policy studies can be distinguished between analysis before and after a specific public policy. Policy analysis before the existence of public policy is based solely on public issues, resulting in truly new public policy recommendations. Both policy analyses before and after the existence of policy have the same goal, which is to provide policy recommendations to policymakers to obtain higher quality policies (Françoise, 2022). Dunn (2000: 117) distinguishes three main forms of public policy analysis:

- 1) Prospective policy analysis.

Prospective Policy Analysis involves the production and transformation of information before policy action begins and is implemented. Policy analysis here is a tool for synthesizing information to be used in formulating comparative policy alternatives and preferences, forecasted in quantitative and qualitative language as a basis or guide in policy decision-making (Cao, 2023).

- 2) Retrospective policy analysis.

Retrospective Policy Analysis is the creation and transformation of information after policy action is taken. There are three types of analysts based on the activities developed by this analyst group, namely discipline-oriented analysts, problem-oriented analysts, and application-oriented analysts. Of course, these three types of retrospective analysis have advantages and disadvantages (Webster, 2022).

- 3) Integrated policy analysis.

Integrated Policy Analysis is a form of analysis that combines the operating styles of practitioners who focus on creating and transforming information before and after policy actions are taken. Integrated policy analysis not only requires analysts to link retrospective and prospective investigation stages but also demands continuous production and transformation of information at all times (Kurebwa, 2020).

The Success of Policy Analysis Methodology according to William N Dunn 2018 is as follows:

1. Structuring Policy Problems: Information about the nature, scope, and severity of problems generated by applying policy analysis procedures to problem structuring (Larsson, 2017).
2. Forecasting Expected Policy Outcomes: A set of procedures to create information about future societal conditions based on current and past information (Dunn, 2021).
3. Prescribing Preferred Policies: Transforming information about expected policy outcomes into information about preferred policies (Dunn, 2018).
4. Monitoring Observed Policy Outcomes: Providing valuable information about what needs to be done to solve problems, only by monitoring the outcomes of a policy can we determine if the policy has been successfully implemented (Dunn, 2018).
5. Evaluating Policy Performance: Making a sharp distinction between fact and value (Marchildon, 2023).

3. Occupational Safety and Health Committee (P2K3)

Minister of Manpower Regulation Number 4 of 1987 regarding Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee and Procedures for the Appointment of Occupational Safety Experts Article 2, requires that every workplace meeting certain criteria, the employer or manager is obliged to establish Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee.

The criteria for the workplace are as follows:

- a) Workplaces where the employer or manager employs 100 or more people.
- b) Workplaces where the employer or manager employs fewer than 100 people but use materials, processes, and installations that have a high risk of explosion, fire, poisoning, and radioactive exposure (Mooney, 2019).

Furthermore, Article 3 (3) states that "Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee is appointed by the Minister or the official designated by him upon the proposal of the relevant employer or manager".

Thus, the initiative to establish Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee in the workplace or company must come from the managers or employers based on awareness to fulfill obligations as stipulated in the legislation (Távora, 2023).

There are several important considerations as the basis for the establishment of Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee. The objective of establishing Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee must ensure that the organization to be formed represents all components in the workplace.

Consultation between management and workers should focus on developing an Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee structure that truly meets the needs of the workplace or company.

When deciding on the organizational needs of Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee that are appropriate for the workplace or company and can meet the demands of legislation (Grupo, 2022), things to consider include:

- The size of the workplace or company
- Operational type and workplace arrangement
- Potential hazards and risk levels in the workplace
- Potential members from each workgroup who will fill the organizational structure.
- Ideal size of the organization that can work effectively.

In large companies or extensive workplaces, a larger number of workgroups will be needed. If Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee has many members, efforts or struggles will be needed to work effectively.

Therefore, it may be necessary to create more than one occupational safety and health organization and then arrange coordination steps among them. It should be realized that too many or too few Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee members will create problems, so an organizational structure that suits the company's needs must be made or arranged (Yang, 2022).

Based on Article 3, Minister of Manpower Regulation Number 4 of 1987 concerning Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee and Procedures for the Appointment of Occupational Safety Experts, it is stated that:

1. The membership of Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee consists of representatives from employers and workers, with a structure consisting of a Chairperson, Secretary, and Members.
2. The Secretary of Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee is an Occupational Safety Expert from the respective company.
3. The Chairperson of Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee is preferably held by the company's management leader or one of the company's managers.

To ensure that the Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee organization functions well, at least half of its members should be from worker representatives (Hall, 2022).

Members from worker representatives, first and foremost, should be selected from individuals with knowledge of work processes and potential hazards in their workplaces.

Similarly, representatives from management or executives should ideally come from managers, supervisors, personnel officers, or OSH professionals who can provide information or input in making company policies, production needs, and other technical aspects of the company (Coulson, 2021).

Furthermore, the ideal number of Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee members for the organization to function effectively is as follows:

1. Companies with a workforce of 100 people or more should have at least 12 members, consisting of 6 worker representatives and 6 representatives from the company's management.
2. Companies with a workforce of 50 to 100 people should have at least 6 members, consisting of 3 worker representatives and 3 representatives from the company's management.
3. Companies with a workforce of fewer than 50 people or workplaces with a high level of risk should have at least 6 members, consisting of 3 worker representatives and 3 representatives from the company's management.

Sometimes it can be very difficult to decide who can be worker representatives and who should be representatives of management, because in most workplaces, everyone is considered "workers" (Moczulska, 2020).

For Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee to work effectively, management representatives should be proposed by management, and worker representatives should be proposed by the workers themselves and not appointed by company managers (Wulandari, 2019).

RESEARCH METHOD

The research method used is qualitative descriptive. According to Silalahi (2015:101), qualitative approach is "an investigation process to understand social problems based on creating a complete holistic picture formed with words, reporting informant views in detail, and arranged in natural data". Sugiyono (2016:11) states that descriptive research is "research conducted to determine the values of independent variables, whether one variable or more, without making comparisons or linking between one variable to another". Furthermore, Sugiyono (2014:147) states that descriptive research is "data analysis conducted by describing or illustrating the collected data as it is without intending to draw conclusions that apply universally or generalizations". This study uses qualitative descriptive method aimed to describe various aspects related to the role of Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee in preventing and reducing work accidents and occupational diseases in the Bukit Indah Purwakarta Industrial Area. With the aim of understanding social problems based on creating a complete holistic picture formed with words, reporting informant views in detail, and arranged in natural data through interview, observation, and documentation techniques (Indrayani, 2020; Susanti, 2019).

After collecting the necessary data, the author conducted analysis through several stages of analysis including:

1. Processing and preparing data for analysis. This step involves interview transcription, scanning material, typing field data, or sorting and arranging the data into different types depending on the source of information (Rahayu, 2023).

2. Reading through all data. At this stage, writing special notes or general ideas about the obtained data (Stuckey, 2015).
3. Starting coding all data. Coding is the process of organizing data by collecting pieces (or parts of text or images) and writing categories within predetermined boundaries before interpreting them (Jensen, 2024).
4. Applying the coding process to describe the settings (domains), people (participants), categories, and themes to be analyzed. This description involves efforts to convey detailed information about people, locations, or events within specific settings (domains) (Marrone, 2022).
5. Showing how these descriptions and themes will be presented again in qualitative narrative/reports (Khoa, 2023).
6. Making interpretations in research or interpreting data (Castleberry, 2018).

DISCUSSION

Based on the above descriptions, the role of Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee in preventing and reducing work accidents and occupational diseases in the industrial area of Bukit Indah Purwakarta using the successful policy analysis methodology according to Dunn (2018) is Structuring Policy Problems, Forecasting Expected Policy Outcomes, Prescribing Preferred Policies, Monitoring Observed Policy Outcomes, and Evaluating Policy Performance.

1. Structuring Policy Problems

Dunn (2013:26) explains in detail that structuring policy problems can help a company to find unseen assumptions, diagnose the causes experienced by the company, map goals that allow combining conflicting general and technical views, and design new policy opportunities that are better. Structuring policy problems is the first step in making public policy by conducting several analyses. Public policy is made because of public problems that occur, so that the problem can be anticipated and achieve the desired goals. Based on the results of interviews and observations conducted by the researcher in the process of identifying problems related to the role of Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee in preventing and reducing work accidents and occupational diseases in the Bukit Indah Purwakarta industrial area, the researcher found the following problems:

- a. Lack of coordination regarding the implementation of occupational safety and health management systems between the company, the Ministry of Manpower, and the Provincial/District Manpower Office, so many companies have not yet received certificates/awards for occupational safety and health management systems from the Ministry of Manpower (Bondroini, 2022; De Los Reyes Martínez Barroso, 2019).
- b. Lack of understanding of the application of occupational safety and health management systems that must be carried out by top management or company executives (Kim, 2017).

- c. Companies are still not obedient and compliant with the obligation to implement occupational safety and health management systems in their companies.
- d. The company's occupational safety and health management system is still below standard (Zhou, 2018).
- e. Provision of human resources with qualifications, job competencies, and authorities in the field of occupational safety and health that are still limited or insufficient (Clearinghouse, 2014).
- f. Inadequate company facilities and infrastructure (Azharuddin, 2022).

2. Forecasting Expected Policy Outcomes

Forecasting provides a prospective vision of policy outcomes, enhancing the capacity to understand, control, and guide society. Forecasts, whether based on expert assessments, extrapolation of historical trends, or sophisticated econometric models, are vulnerable to errors based on false or unreasonable assumptions, unknown effects of institutional incentive systems, and the complexity of policy issues in areas ranging from health, welfare, and education to science, technology, and the environment (Dunn, 2021).

Forecasting is a set of procedures for creating information about the future state of society based on current and past information. Forecasts take three main forms: extrapolation, prediction, and expert assessment (Moriarty, 2023; Lorenzo Sánchez, 2019).

Based on the results of interviews and observations conducted by the researcher in the process of predicting future policy, it was found that the role of Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee in preventing and reducing work accidents and occupational diseases in the Bukit Indah Purwakarta industrial area requires the addition of occupational safety and health personnel, provision of safety and health infrastructure, improvement of occupational safety and health management system standards, and preparation of human resources with qualifications, job competencies, and authorities in the field of occupational safety and health as four main points that are interrelated in the role of Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee in preventing and reducing work accidents and occupational diseases in the Bukit Indah Purwakarta industrial area (Rahmat, 2023).

3. Prescribing Preferred Policies

The methodology of prescribing transforms information about expected policy outcomes into information about preferred policies. To prescribe policies requires prior information about the expected outcomes of choosing among alternative policies. However, prescribing methodology also requires us to have information about which outcomes are more valuable than others. For this reason, prescribing is inherently normative and closely related to ethical and moral issues (Dunn, 2018; Dolfmsma, 2020).

Based on the results of interviews and observations conducted by the researcher in the process of policy recommendation, it was found that technical regulations related to the implementation of occupational safety and health management systems are still needed in the Bukit Indah

Purwakarta industrial area. In addition, there is still a need to increase the understanding capability of top management or company executives in the obligation to implement occupational safety and health management systems (Brown, 2018).

4. Monitoring Observed Policy Outcomes

Monitoring allows the production of information about the causes and consequences of policy. Because monitoring investigates the relationship between policy operations and observed outcomes, it is the primary source of information about the success of efforts to implement policy. Monitoring goes beyond normative prescriptions of economic analysis by setting factual premises about policy. Monitoring is primarily concerned with setting factual premises about public policy, while evaluation is concerned with setting value premises. While factual and value premises continue to change, and "facts" and "values" are interdependent, only monitoring yields factual claims during and after policies are adopted and implemented (ex post) (Korneilis, 2018; Atarah, 2023).

Monitoring serves several functions in policy analysis: compliance, auditing, accounting, and description and explanation (Xu, 2021).

Based on the results of interviews and observations conducted by the researcher in the process of monitoring or policy monitoring, it was found that monitoring is indeed conducted, but the results sometimes do not become input to the discussions conducted for each policy taken by the government, only as a punch list for companies to take corrective action (Hafeez, 2022).

5. Evaluating Policy Performance

Evaluation as a type of causal assessment helps generate information about the role of Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee in preventing and reducing work accidents and occupational related diseases in the Bukit Indah Purwakarta industrial area against outcomes. When discussing ethics and values in the role of Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee in preventing and reducing work accidents and occupational diseases, some analysts believe that policy evaluation should focus on explanation and prediction, treating ethics and values as reflections. Policy disagreement will decrease or disappear, argue "predictivists," if analysts can predict with greater certainty. It is useless to spend a lot of time on fundamental value differences because they are debated and difficult to resolve (Mergoni, 2022). Based on the results of interviews and observations conducted by the researcher in the process of evaluating policy performance, it was found that the technical evaluation process is actually the responsibility of all policy stakeholders involved in preventing and reducing work accidents and occupational related diseases in the Bukit Indah Purwakarta industrial area, but for problems that occur in the scope of increasing the understanding capability of top management or company executives in the obligation to implement occupational safety and health management systems become the responsibility of the Central and Regional Governments as well as Companies. Therefore, the evaluation and monitoring processes must be carried out by all stakeholders, so that the progress of the action plan to be prepared next can be realized properly (Daoden, 2019).

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis results and field findings presented above, the researcher can conclude that in preventing and reducing work accidents and occupational diseases in the Bukit Indah Purwakarta industrial area, the role of Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee has not been implemented properly and maximally. This is due to the continued occurrence of work accidents. These companies still need support in the form of supervision and guidance on compliance with the implementation of occupational safety and health management systems according to Government Regulation No. 50 of 2012 (Alfian, R., 2024; Liu, 2022).

The dominance of top management in companies is seen from initiation to decision making related to annual work plans submitted by occupational safety and health experts. This condition is known and acknowledged by various parties encountered by the researcher such as several company occupational safety and health expert staff, managers of the Bukit Indah Purwakarta industrial area, SMK3 auditors, labor unions, and even occupational safety and health experts in association gatherings to several employees at the Ministry of Manpower and Provincial/District Manpower Offices. Therefore, if mapped, the role of Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee or company management/team is in a primary or important position in planning compliance and adherence to preventing and reducing work accidents and occupational diseases in the Bukit Indah Purwakarta industrial area. The following are the research findings from the role of Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee in preventing and reducing work accidents and occupational diseases in the Bukit Indah Purwakarta industrial area (Mogård, 2023; Racicot, 2019).

1. In the policy issue arrangement stage, researchers found problems such as a lack of coordination in the implementation of occupational safety and health management systems between companies, the Indonesian Ministry of Manpower (Kemnaker RI), and the Provincial/District Manpower Offices. Consequently, many companies have yet to receive certificates/awards for occupational safety and health management systems from Kemnaker RI. There is still a lack of understanding among top management or company executives regarding the implementation of occupational safety and health management systems (Widianingsih, 2007). Companies still do not fully comply with their obligations to implement occupational safety and health management systems. The occupational safety and health management systems of companies are still below standard. The provision of human resources with qualifications, job competency, and authority in the field of occupational safety and health is limited or insufficient. Company facilities and infrastructure are inadequate (Lamba, 2019).
2. In the stage of predicting expected policy outcomes, several issues were identified: the need for additional occupational safety and health personnel, provision of occupational safety and health facilities and infrastructure, improvement of occupational safety and health management system standards, and preparation of human resources with qualifications, job competency, and authority in the field of occupational safety and health. These four interconnected points play a significant role in the function of the Occupational Safety and Health Committee in preventing and reducing work accidents and work-related illnesses in

- the industrial area of the beautiful hill city of Purwakarta (Raharja, 2017); Haslam, C., 2016).
3. In the stage of selecting policy options, several issues were identified: the need for technical regulations related to the implementation of occupational safety and health management systems in the industrial area of the beautiful hill city of Purwakarta. Additionally, there is still a need to enhance the understanding and capacity of top management or company executives regarding their obligations in implementing occupational safety and health management systems (Raharja, 2018; Kadir, 2022).
 4. In the stage of monitoring observed policy outcomes, several issues were found: although monitoring or supervision of occupational safety and health is conducted, the results sometimes do not contribute to discussions on policies made by the government, serving merely as a punch list for companies to take corrective action (MS, Z. H., & Rizaldi, 2020).
 5. During the policy performance evaluation stage, several issues were identified: the technical evaluation process is the responsibility of all policy stakeholders involved in implementing occupational safety and health management systems in the industrial area of the beautiful hill city of Purwakarta. However, addressing issues related to enhancing the understanding and capacity of top management or company executives in their obligations to implement occupational safety and health management systems falls under the responsibility of the Central and Regional Governments as well as Companies (Widianingsih, 2019). Therefore, the evaluation and monitoring processes must involve all stakeholders to ensure the successful realization of subsequent action plans. The role of Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee in preventing and reducing work accidents and work-related illnesses in the industrial area of the beautiful hill city of Purwakarta is still not optimal. The implementation of occupational safety and health management systems in the industrial area does not meet established standards, and work accidents still occur, posing serious risks to the safety and health of workers (Alfian, R., 2024). Hence, policy improvements regulating the role of Occupational Safety and Health Advisory Committee in preventing and reducing work accidents and work-related illnesses in the industrial area of the beautiful hill city of Purwakarta are still necessary (Pillay, 2015).

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